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Remarking An Analisation

Loopholes Under The NDPS Act, 1985

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Abstract

The Narcotics Drug and Psychotropic Substances (NDPS) Act, 1985 was enacted in response to the treaty obligation of India under the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961, as amended by the 1972 Protocol and the Convention on Psychotropic Substances of 1971, to control the increasing trend in drug abuse and illicit drug trafficking. The NDPS Act prohibits a person from engaging in any activity relating to the cultivation, production, transport, storage, sale, purchase and consumption of any narcotic or psychotropic drug without authorised permission. Generally, narcotic drugs cause sleep, while psychotropic substances have properties that can alter an individual's mind. The NDPS Act bans nearly 200 psychotropic substances. These drugs can be sold only when a prescription is produced. Violation of the provisions of this law may result in a punishment which includes rigorous imprisonment or, fine or both and, in exceptional cases, even the death penalty. Still, if the drugs have been used for personal consumption, then a lesser punishment may be awarded subject to the fulfilment of certain conditions. Within a span of around 40 years, the NDPS Act has been amended four times by way of Amendment Act 2 of 1989, Act 9 of 2001, Act 16 of 2014 and Act 48 of 2021. Despite these amendments to the NDPS Act, still there are many flaws/loopholes that require redressal in order to achieve the Act's primary objective because many offenders have been acquitted due to non-compliance of mandatory and directory provisions by the authorities as prescribed in the Act. These acquittals have created a sense of insecurity in the society.

Keywords Narcotics Drug, Psychotropic Substances, Illicit Trafficking, Non-Compliance, Mandatory and Directory Provisions.

Introduction

One of the most pressing global problems today is the epidemic of drug addiction and the illegal trade in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances. Addiction to drugs poses serious risks to public health and significant challenges to preserving public safety and national security. Consequently, it has far-reaching consequences for society as a whole. Previously, the issue of drug trafficking was concern of only a limited countries who were affected from it; but, nowadays, the entire international community is concerned about it. The complexities related to the problem of drugs have grown to such an extent that every country in the world are concerned about it and is trying to strengthen their legal frameworks to safeguard their national interests. Due to its geographical location, India has emerged as a pivotal transit center for the trafficking of illicit drugs. The porous nature of the borders between India and Pakistan, India and Nepal, as well as India and Myanmar, have extremely complicated the interception of drug trafficking. The Supreme Court has also highlighted the adverse effects of drug abuse and its trafficking in the case of *State of Punjab v. Baldev Singh*[1], has observed:-

“Drug abuse is a social malady. While drug addiction eats into the vitals of society, drug trafficking not only eats into the vitals of the economy of a country but illicit money generated by drug trafficking is often used for illicit activities, including the encouragement of terrorism. There is no doubt that drug trafficking, trading and its use, which is a global phenomenon and has acquired the dimensions of an epidemic, affects the economic policies of the State, corrupts the system and is detrimental to the future of a country. It has the effect of producing a sick society and a harmful culture. Anti-drug justice is a criminal dimension of social justice. The United Nations Conventions against Illicit Trafficking in Narcotic Drugs & Psychotropic Substances, which was held in Vienna,

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Austria, in 1988, was perhaps one of the first efforts, at an international level, to tackle the menace of drug trafficking throughout the comity of nations. The Government of India has ratified this convention."

The NDPS Act of 1985 was enacted to control the increasing drug abuse and trafficking of illicit narcotics drug and psychotropic substances. The Act is a comprehensive legislation covering every aspect concerning narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances. Since its enactment, the Act has been amended four times: by way of Amendments Act 2 of 1989, Act 9 of 2001, Act 16 of 2014, and Act 48 of 2021. Despite these amendments, still in the NDPS Act, there are many flaws/loopholes that need to be redressed to achieve the Act's primary objective.

Objective of study

In this article, the researcher has attempted to analyse the efficacy of various provisions of the NDPS Act, 1985, in the light of judicial pronouncement to point out the shortcomings of the Act.

Review of Literature

Key journal article , books and relevant cases have been reviewed for this paper which have been discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

Loopholes in the NDPS Act

A few noticeable deficiencies/loopholes in this Act are discussed below:-

Precursor Chemicals

By analysing the current trend of illicit drug trafficking in India, it can be said that India is one of the major producers and exporters of precursor chemicals in the world. Without these chemicals, it is impossible to convert raw drugs into synthetic drugs. Under the NDPS Act, the word 'Controlled Substances' has been used for these types of chemicals and brought under the Regulation of Control Substances Order 2013. There is no classification based on the quantity of these chemicals, as was done by the amendment of 2001 in the case of other drugs. Therefore, the punishment provided for contravention of an order under Section 9A, which has been provided under Section 25A, is uniform, i.e. rigorous imprisonment (RI) of up to 10 years and a fine up to ₹ 1,00,000 (the court may impose fine exceeding this by recording reason in the judgement). Considering the new trends of precursor trafficking, it is necessary that these precursor chemicals be classified into small and commercial quantities, and further, the punishment should be determined accordingly.

Remand Orders

As per Section 36A (1)(b)[2] of the NDPS Act, the Judicial Magistrate has been empowered to detain and remand an arrestee to the custody for a period not more than 15 days in whole. Except for the commercial quantity offences, the NDPS Act has nowhere provided the outer period of detention as has been provided under Section 187 (2) and Section 187 (3) of the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita(BNSS), 2023 [earlier section 167 (2) of Cr.P.C]. This vagueness has resulted into different interpretations by various courts[3]. Some High Courts have held that after 15 days, the Judicial Magistrate becomes functus-officio. The accused person is required to be produced before a Special Judge for further remands. At the same time, some have held that till such courts are not constituted for the purpose, the Magistrate can remand the accused person even beyond the period of 15 days[4] and beyond 90 days[5] also. Therefore this defect should be clarified through amendment.

Section 187 (3)[6] of BNSS provides that depending upon the gravity of the offence, if it is not possible to complete the investigation in 60 days/90 days, then the accused is entitled to mandatory bail under Section 187 (3) of BNSS if he makes an application in this regard and furnishes bail. At the same time, Section 36A (4)[7] of the NDPS Act provides to increase the maximum period of 90 days provided under section 187 (3) of BNSS to 180 days for persons liable under Section 19 or Section 24 or Section 27A of the NDPS Act, or offences relating to commercial quantity. As per the proviso to the sub-section, detention up to one year can be extended on the condition that the public prosecutor submits a report which must indicate the progress of the investigation and the reasons for seeking detention beyond the period of 180 days. This provision under the NDPS Act is totally against the principles of speedy trial enshrined in the Constitution of India. It violates the fundamental human right of an accused person to get justice in the stipulated time and needs to be amended. There is no need to give more time to complete the investigation; otherwise, the very purpose of the NDPS Act will be frustrated.

Bail

Under Section 36A of the NDPS Act, the Judicial Magistrate has been empowered (impliedly) to try the offences punishable for a term of 3 years and less by adopting summary procedure under 36A (5)[8] of the NDPS Act. Though trial powers have been conferred to the Judicial Magistrate by the 2001 amendment, the powers to accept bail prayers have never been conferred. Under proviso to Section 36A (1)(b)[9] it is required that the Magistrate should forward the arrestee to the Special Courts constituted for the purpose, if the Magistrate found such detention unnecessary. Therefore, it is submitted that even in petty offences, this proviso is acting as a prohibition upon the powers of the Judicial Magistrate to grant bail to the accused person.[10] Necessary amendment is needed to make in this provision so that the ambiguity may be removed.

Punishment

Section 27[11] of the NDPS Act deals with the illicit possession of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances for personal usage in small quantities. Before the 2001 amendment, vide Notification No. S.O. 827 (E) dated 14th Nov. 1985, the Government of India determined the small quantity of five drugs, namely: Heroin, Hashish or Charas, Opium, Ganja and Cocaine.[12] After 2001 amendment, the Government of India vide Notification No. 1055 (E) dated 19th Oct. 2001[13] has upwardly revised the small quantity of the drugs as mentioned above. The following table shows the difference between the two notifications:-

Name of the Drugs	Small Quantity (Pre 2001)	Small Quantity (Post 2001)	Ratio of Increase
Hashish or Charas	5 gms.	100 gms.	20 times
Heroin	250 mgs.	5 gms.	20 times
Cocaine	125 mgs.	2 gms.	16 times
Opium	5 gms.	25 gms.	5 times
Ganja	500 gms.	1000 gms.	2 times

From the above table it is clear that Government of India, despite the fact that the drug menace is growing day by day and has emerged as one of the biggest socio-economic problem, has enhanced the quantity of drugs under the small quantity category which is against the mandate of the NDPS Act. Therefore, it is submitted that the above matter requires reconsideration, and the government should take appropriate steps to remove this anomaly to achieve the dream of a free society.

After 2001 amendment, the punishment has been provided according to the quantity of drugs. Small quantity and Commercial quantity has been notified by the Central Government vide Notification No. 1055 (E) dated 19th Oct. 2001.[14] For intermediate quantity the range is between the small quantity and commercial quantity.

S. No.	Name of Narcotic Drug/Psychotropic Substance	Small Quantity (in gm.)	Commercial Quantity (in gm./kg.)
1.	Alprazolam	5 gm	100 gm
2.	Amphetamine	2 gm	50 gm
3.	Buprenorphine	1 gm	20 gm
4.	Cannabis or its resin/Charas/Hashish	100 gm	1 kg
5.	Cocaine	2 gm	100 gm
6.	Codeine	10 gm	1 kg
7.	Diazepam	20 gm	500 gm
8.	Ganja	1000 gm	20 kg
9.	Heroin	5 gm	250 gm
10.	Ketamine ¹⁵	10 gm	500 gm
11.	Lysergide/ LSD	0.002 gm	0.1 gm
12.	MDMA/Ecstasy	0.5 gm	10 gm
13.	Methamphetamine	2 gm	50 gm
14.	Methadone	2 gm	50 gm
15.	Methaqualone	20 gm	500 gm
16.	Morphine	5 gm	250 gm
17.	Opium	25 gm	2.5 kg
18.	Opium Derivatives	5 gm	250 gm
19.	Poppy straw	1000 gm	50 kg
20.	Tramadol ¹⁶	5 gm	250 gm

Punishment for small quantity: - Maximum 1 year rigorous imprisonment (RI) or a fine up to ₹ 10,000 or both.

Punishment for commercial quantity: - RI from 10 years (minimum) to 20 years (maximum) and a fine from ₹ 1-2 lakhs.

Punishment for intermediate quantity: - RI that may extend to 10 years and fine that may extend to ₹ 1 lakh.

From the above table, it is evident that there are vast gaps between small quantities and commercial quantities in some cases. E.g. for Cannabis and Cannabis resin, the range is between 100 and 1,000 grams; for Ganja, between 1 kg and 20 kg; for Herion and Morphine, 5 and 250 grams, respectively; opium, 25 grams and 2.5 kg; for Poppy straw, 1 kg and 50 kg. This means that the legislature has wholly left it to the judiciary to decide the case according to discretion. In the case of commercial quantity, there is no upper limit. It has been observed that there is no uniformity in the sentencing of the courts. It has been noticed that in several cases for the seizure of 20 kg of Charas, the punishment awarded was 10 years imprisonment and ₹ 1,00,000 fine, while for the seizure of 1.26 kg of Charas, the punishment was more or less the same. Similarly, for the seizure of 20 kg of Heroin, the sentence awarded was 15 years imprisonment and ₹ 1,50,000 fine. In contrast, for the same seizure quantity in another case, the punishment awarded was 10 years imprisonment and ₹ 1,00,000 fine. Therefore, there is clearly a disparity in sentencing of the courts, and the same needs to be removed by amendment.

No Suspension, Remission or Commutation of Sentence Awarded

Section 32A[17] of the Act provides that "no sentence awarded under this Act (other than section 27) shall be suspended or remitted or commuted." Only the offenders below the age of 18 years or convicted for abuse of drugs in small quantities have been excluded. [18] The amendment Act of 2001, 2014 and 2021 have also over-looked the judgement of the Supreme Court which has been given in the case of *Dadu v. State of Maharashtra*[19], wherein the court has declared Section 32A partially unconstitutional, i.e. "it is unconstitutional to the extent it takes away the right of the court to suspend the sentence of a convict under the Act" but at the same time the section is constitutionally valid in so far as it takes away the right of the Executive to suspend or remit or commute the sentence of a convict. Therefore, this draconian provision under the Act needs to be corrected immediately in the light of Supreme Court judgement.

Witness

Section 50[20] of the NDPS Act required the presence of a Gazetted Officer or a Magistrate at the time of search of any person. Undoubtedly, this provision has been made for the benefit of the accused in the sense that a search before such an officer will rule out the possibility of planting drugs. However, from the administrative point of view,

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it becomes practically impossible to arrange such an officer at a time, and the situation worsens in the case of chance recovery. The other aspect is that generally drug raids are usually conducted at night, and it is impractical to arrange such an officer before searching for the person, particularly when the incident took place in a remote area. However, the search can be conducted by an authorised officer under Section 42 of the NDPS Act, under the provision of Section 103 of BNSS (earlier section 100 of Cr.P.C.) if it is not possible to take such person to the Gazetted Officer or Magistrate. However, Section 103 (4)[21] of BNSS states that it is mandatory that at least two respectable local residents must be present before the conduct of search and seizure. Again, from the administrative point of view, it is challenging to arrange two respectable people from the locality at night and in a remote area because nowadays, respectable citizens are not willing to indulge in any sort of legal procedures. Further, in various cases, it has been seen that the public witnesses have turned hostile in the court of law and changed their statements because of bribes taken or threat of life by the drug traffickers and many other reasons. Therefore, considering the administrative view, suitable amendments may be made, and video recording of search and seizure with time, date, and GPS-based location should be made compulsory.

Immunity from Prosecution

Section 64A[22] of the NDPS Act provides for immunity from prosecution to the addict who is volunteering for treatment, i.e. if any person has been charged for an offence under Section 27 of the Act and shows his/her willingness to undergo treatment for de-addiction under a government approved hospital or institution, such person may be granted immunity from the prosecution subject to complete treatment. Undoubtedly, the intention of the legislature is to provide an opportunity for the addict to rehabilitate. However, it has been seen that after taking the benefit of immunity from prosecution and de-addiction treatment several times, the addicts have started abusing drugs again when they come in contact with peer groups.

No Provision for Life Imprisonment

One of the major loopholes of the NDPS Act is that there is no provision for life imprisonment. The punishment in the Act ranges from 10 years to 20, and, in exceptional cases, even the death penalty for repeat offences. In many cases, it has been that after serving imprisonment, the drug traffickers have again been involved in the trafficking trade. Therefore, the provision of life imprisonment to the traffickers with commercial quantity and repeated offenders should be immediately made by the suitable amendment in the Act because the sentence of life imprisonment has more deterrence effects than imprisonment for 10 or 20 years.

No Provision for Online/Internet Pharmacy

One of the major loopholes in the NDPS Act is that there is no provision to deal with the online sale of pharmaceutical drugs, particularly those drugs which contain narcotic and psychotropic components. Even the Drugs and Cosmetics Act 1940 and the Drugs and Cosmetics Rules 1945 also have no provisions to deal with internet pharmacies. [23] There are several instances where illicit internet pharmacies have been busted by drug enforcement agencies, and tablets containing narcotic/psychotropic components have been seized. In *Zaheer Ahmed v. Union of India & Anr.*[24] the Delhi High Court has ordered a country wide- ban on the sale of online drugs until a relevant legal framework for such sale is enforced. Following the High Court order, the Drugs Controller General of India has imposed a blanket ban on selling medicines through unlicensed virtual pharmacies until further notice.[25] Therefore, taking into consideration the potential abuse of such drugs, the Government of India should notify the rules governing the online sale of drugs, and prescription should be mandatory to have a drug containing narcotic/psychotropic components. There should be proper monitoring of abuse of a common prescription to buy such drugs from different platforms.

Conclusion

Despite the loopholes/technical flaws mentioned above, the NDPS Act has been able to combat the issue of drug abuse and its illicit trafficking, but the desired result is yet to be achieved. The judiciary has undoubtedly played an essential role in interpreting and implementing various provisions of the NDPS Act and the BNSS (earlier Cr.P.C), particularly regarding search, seizure, arrest and investigation. In multiple cases, the judiciary has brought the procedural lacunas by the hand of the investigating agency. The observation or the directives given by the courts are acting as guidelines in those areas. The Legislature has also acted on the judiciary's observations and has amended the Act accordingly to remove the procedural lacunas. Hence, the NDPS Act may be amended again, considering the loopholes/technical flaws mentioned above.

Endnote

1. (1999) 6 SCC 172
2. The Narcotics Drug and Psychotropic Substances (NDPS) Act, 1985, (Act 61 of 1985) s. 36A (1)(b) where a person accused of or suspected of the commission of an offence

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under this Act is forwarded to a Magistrate under sub-section (2) or sub-section (2A) of section 167 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (2 of 1974), such Magistrate may authorise the detention of such person in such custody as he thinks fit for a period not exceeding fifteen days in the whole where such Magistrate is a Judicial Magistrate and seven days in the whole where such Magistrate is an Executive Magistrate:

Provided that in cases which are triable by the Special Court where such Magistrate considers

(i) when such person is forwarded to him as aforesaid; or

(ii) upon or at any time before the expiry of the period of detention authorised by him, that the detention of such person is unnecessary, he shall order such person to be forwarded to the Special Court having jurisdiction;

3. B. D. Agarwal, "NDPS Act- Legislative Loopholes" January Cri.L.J 2 (2006).

4. Janta Singh v. State of Punjab, 1996 Cri.L.J 1185.

5. Bimbadhar Behera v. State of Orissa, MANU/OR/0181/1993

6. The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023 (Act 46 of 2023) s. 187 (3) The Magistrate may authorise the detention of the accused person, beyond the period of fifteen days, if he is satisfied that adequate grounds exist for doing so, but no Magistrate shall authorise the detention of the accused person in custody under this sub-section for a total period exceeding—

(i) ninety days, where the investigation relates to an offence punishable with death, imprisonment for life or imprisonment for a term of ten years or more;

(ii) sixty days, where the investigation relates to any other offence,

and, on the expiry of the said period of ninety days, or sixty days, as the case may be, the accused person shall be released on bail if he is prepared to and does furnish bail, and every person released on bail under this sub-section shall be deemed to be so released under the provisions of Chapter XXXV for the purposes of that Chapter.

7. Supra note 2, s. 36A (4) In respect of persons accused of an offence punishable under section 19 or section 24 or section 27A or for offences involving commercial quantity the references in sub-section (2) of section 167 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (2 of 1974) thereof to "ninety days", where they occur, shall be construed as reference to "one hundred and eighty days":

Provided that, if it is not possible to complete the investigation within the said period of one hundred and eighty days, the Special Court may extend the said period up to one year on the report of the Public Prosecutor indicating the progress of the investigation and the specific reasons for the detention of the accused beyond the said period of one hundred and eighty days.

8. Id., s. 36A (5) Notwithstanding anything contained in the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (2 of 1974), the offences punishable under this Act with imprisonment for a term of not more than three years may be tried summarily.

9. Supra note 2

10. Supra note 3 at p 3.

11. Supra note 2, s. 27. Punishment for consumption of any narcotic drug or psychotropic substance.—Whoever, consumes any narcotic drug or psychotropic substance shall be punishable,—

(a) where the narcotic drug or psychotropic substance consumed is cocaine, morphine, diacetyl-morphine or any other narcotic drug or any psychotropic substance as may be specified in this behalf by the Central Government by notification in the Official Gazette, with rigorous imprisonment for a term which may extend to one year, or with fine which may extend to twenty thousand rupees; or with both; and

(b) where the narcotic drug or psychotropic substance consumed is other than those specified in or under clause (a), with imprisonment for a term which may extend to six months, or with fine which may extend to ten thousand rupees, or with both.

12. Tripti Tandon, "Addicts to Convict: Working of the NDPS Act in Punjab- A Critique", The Leaflet, Sep. 7, 2018 also available at: <https://theleaflet.in/addict-to-convict-working-of-the-ndps-act-in-punjab-a-critique-vidhi-centre-lawyers-collective/> (last visited on March 25, 2025).

13. Notification Specifying Small Quantity and Commercial Quantity, Government of India, Ministry of Finance (Department of Revenue), available at: <http://cbn.nic.in/pdf/qtynotif.pdf> (last visited on March 26, 2025).

14. Ibid.

15. Notification S. O. 1430 (E) dated 21st June 2011, Government of India, Ministry of Finance (Department of Revenue), available at: https://dor.gov.in/files/notifications_documents/SO1430E.pdf (last visited on March 28, 2025).

16. Notification S. O. 1762 (E) dated 26th April 2018, Government of India, Ministry of Finance (Department of Revenue), available at:

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<https://narcoticsindia.nic.in/Notifications/Tramadol%20Notification-%20185016.pdf> (last visited on March 28, 2025).

17. Supra note 2, s. 32A. No suspension, remission or commutation in any sentence awarded under this Act. - Notwithstanding anything contained in the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (2 of 1974), or any other law for the time being in force but subject to the provisions of section 33, no sentence awarded under this Act (other than section 27) shall be suspended or remitted or commuted.

18. Id., s. 33. Application of section 360 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 and of the Probation of Offenders Act, 1958.—Nothing contained in section 360 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (2 of 1974) or in the Probation of Offenders Act, 1958 (20 of 1958) shall apply to a person convicted of an offence under this Act unless such person is under eighteen years of age or that the offence for which such person is convicted is punishable under section 26 or section 27.

19. 2000 Cri L.J 4619.

20. Supra note 2, s. 50. Conditions under which search of persons shall be conducted.—

(1) When any officer duly authorised under section 42 is about to search any person under the provisions of section 41, section 42 or section 43, he shall, if such person so requires, take such person without unnecessary delay to nearest Gazetted Officer of any of the departments mentioned in section 42 or to the nearest Magistrate.

(2) If such requisition is made, the officer may detain the person until he can bring him before the Gazetted Officer or the Magistrate referred to in sub-section (1).

(3) The Gazetted Officer or the Magistrate before whom any such person is brought shall, if he sees no reasonable ground for search, forthwith discharge the person but otherwise shall direct that search be made.

(4) No female shall be searched by anyone excepting a female.

(5) When an officer duly authorised under section 42 has reason to believe that it is not possible to take the person to be searched to the nearest Gazetted Officer or Magistrate without the possibility of the person to be searched parting with possession of any narcotic drug or psychotropic substance, or controlled substance or article or document, he may, instead of taking such person to the nearest Gazetted Officer or Magistrate, proceed to search the person as provided under section 100 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (2 of 1974).

(6) After a search is conducted under sub-section (5), the officer shall record the reasons for such belief which necessitated such search and within seventy-two hours send a copy thereof to his immediate official superior.

21. Supra note 6, s. 103 (4) Before making a search under this Chapter, the officer or other person about to make it shall call upon two or more independent and respectable inhabitants of the locality in which the place to be searched is situate or of any other locality if no such inhabitant of the said locality is available or is willing to be a witness to the search, to attend and witness the search and may issue an order in writing to them or any of them so to do.

22. Supra note 2, s. 64A. Immunity from prosecution to addicts volunteering for treatment. - Any addict, who is charged with an offence punishable under section 27 or with offences involving small quantity of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances, who voluntarily seeks to undergo medical treatment for de-addiction from a hospital or an institution maintained or recognised by the Government or a local authority and undergoes such treatment shall not be liable to prosecution under section 27 or under any other section for offences involving small quantity of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances:

Provided that the said immunity from prosecution may be withdrawn if the addict does not undergo the complete treatment for de-addiction.

23. Himani Chandna, "Year after HC order, Modi govt to act against e-pharmacies selling drugs without licences" The Print, Dec. 3, 2019 also available at: <https://theprint.in/india/governance/year-after-hc-order-modi-govt-to-act-against-e-pharmacies-selling-drugs-without-licences/329537/> (last visited on March 29, 2025).

24. Writ Petition (C) No:11711/2018

25. Nupur Thapliyal "Frame Policy On Online Sale Of Drugs Within Eight Weeks, Else Joint Secretary Should Appear: Delhi High Court To Centre" Live Law.in, Nov. 16, 2023 also available at: <https://www.livelaw.in/high-court/delhi-high-court/delhi-high-court-policy-online-sale-drugs-centre-242358> (last visited on March 30, 2025).